

Australian Research Data Commons

ARDC FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs)

A questionnaire to support FIP creation for data outputs in ARDC Co-investment Projects

ARDC Expertise and Skilled Workforce Development Teams

1 September 2025

CONTENTS

About FAIR	1
FAIR Implementation Profiles	1
The ARDC's FAIR Policy and Guidelines	2
The ARDC FIP Questionnaire	2
1. Create a copy of the FIP Questionnaire	2
2. Complete the FIP Questionnaire	3
Acknowledgement	3

About FAIR

An abbreviation for “findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable”, the [FAIR Principles](#) provide a framework for sharing data in a way that maximises its use and reuse.

The FAIR Principles emerged from Wilkinson et al.’s 2016 journal article “[FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship](#)”. Developed by the international research community, these principles aim to:

- support knowledge discovery and innovation both by humans and machines
- facilitate data and knowledge integration
- enable new discoveries through the analysis of multiple datasets
- promote the sharing and reuse of data
- apply across multiple disciplines, including those with sensitive data
- strive for machine-readable data and metadata.

The FAIR Principles provide guidelines to improve the findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of digital objects. These principles do not necessitate data being “open” or “free”, but they do require clarity and transparency around the conditions governing data access and reuse. You can learn more about FAIR on the ARDC’s website:

- Learn more about [making your data FAIR](#)
- Find more [training resources on FAIR](#)

FAIR Implementation Profiles

[GO FAIR](#) is an international initiative designing and building technical standards, best practices and infrastructure components to support the implementation of the FAIR Data Principles. [FAIR Implementation Profiles](#) (FIPs) are a methodology developed by GO FAIR through which a community expresses its practices and decisions around each of the FAIR Guiding Principles. The approach involves a series of questions on how the community makes data and metadata FAIR and what ‘FAIR Enabling Resources’ (FERs) are used.

The [GO FAIR FIP Mini Questionnaire](#) captures FIPs using a series of questions intended to elicit answers that explicitly profile the FAIR implementation approach of a community. This Mini-Questionnaire can then be used to support the completion of a FIP as a reusable machine-readable nano-publication in [GO FAIR’s FIP Wizard](#). Published FIPs and FERs can be searched in [FAIR Connect](#).

The ARDC's FAIR Policy and Guidelines

The ARDC's [FAIR Policy](#) requires the application of the FAIR principles to ARDC's own materials as well as to materials from co-invested projects. In addition, for **co-investment projects producing data outputs**, the [FAIR Guideline for ARDC Co-Investment Project Data Outputs](#) applies. This Guideline requires that Project Plans include a FAIR initiation activity as part of a Work Package. The FAIR initiation activity is facilitated by ARDC Skills Leads and captures decisions or plans for implementation of FAIR for the project's data outputs, in a simple template modelled on [GO FAIR's FIP Mini Questionnaire](#). The responses in the Questionnaire can be updated, or added to, over the course of the project.

Any projects that would like to go further, e.g. with using the GO FAIR FIP Wizard, to store and formally publish FIPs, can be supported by ARDC to do so.

The ARDC FIP Questionnaire

ARDC Co-investment Projects can follow the steps below to create a copy of the Questionnaire for completion:

1. Create a copy of the FIP Questionnaire

Log in to a Google account and click the "Access Now" button below.

An online copy of the Questionnaire will be created as a Google Sheet in your personal drive (MyDrive). Don't forget to share this document with relevant ARDC staff.

It is best to work with the tool as a Google Sheet online, however you can download the Google Sheet as an Excel spreadsheet, noting that the dropdown selections in the third tab will only be visible when you click in each cell.

Access Now

2. Complete the FIP Questionnaire

Once you have made a copy of the Google Sheet, then complete the third tab of the spreadsheet for the anticipated data outputs from your project (i.e. complete column D-E to reflect the FAIR implementation choices for this project's data outputs).

The FIP Questionnaire should be completed during a meeting with your ARDC Skills Lead - this is the FAIR Initiation Activity referred to in the Guidelines. Or if you prefer, it can be completed prior to the meeting, and a short review session may then only be required. Please discuss your preferred approach with your ARDC Program Manager/Coordinator and/or Skills Lead. The completed FIP Questionnaire should be included when submitting progress or final reports to the ARDC.

Optional:

If you would like to capture a record of progress in relation to FAIR during the project, you can complete a second copy of the FIP Questionnaire again at the end of the project, which can be compared with the first.

Acknowledgement

This FIP Mini Questionnaire is adapted for ARDC from [the original](#) developed by Barbara Magagna, Marek Suchanek, Tobias Kuhn, and Erik Schultes and has its origins in the [GO FAIR FAIR Convergence Matrix \(& FIP\) Working Group](#).

Please contact ARDC with any suggestions for improvement.